

COMPAS

Checking on Mental Health
Providing Alternatives to Suicide

Implementation Guide for COMPAS

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Table of Contents

Acknowledgement of Country	3
Acknowledgement of Lived Experience	3
Value Statement	3
A Note About Language	3
Myths and Misconceptions of Suicide	4
Program Objectives	5
COMPAS Principles	5
COMPAS and Improving Early Identification	5
Background	6
Survey Management	7
The COMPAS Model: Flowchart	8
Data Management	9
Identity Verification	9
De-identification of Personal Information	9
Disclosure of Personal Information	10
Information Use	10
Training Requirements	11
General Training Requirements	11
General Responsibilities	11
Telephone Assessment Team	12
Survey Management Team	12
COMPAS Staff Recruitment	13
Training and Support	13
Key Personnel	14
Implementation	15
Survey Recruitment	15
Specific Safety Considerations	15
Public Mental Health Services	15
On-Campus Services	16
	17

Acknowledgement of Country

In the spirit of reconciliation, we acknowledge the Traditional Custodians of Country throughout Australia and their connections to land, sea, and community. We pay our respect to their Elders past and present and extend that respect to all Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples today.

Acknowledgment of Lived Experience

We acknowledge the valuable perspectives of those with lived experience of suicidal thoughts and behaviours. We honour those lost to suicide, and acknowledge the tragedy of these losses for all those involved. We understand that lived experience is paramount to each and every area of suicide policy, prevention, intervention, and research.

Value Statement

COMPAS was created to enable person-centred, strengths-focused support to meet university students' needs of enhanced wellbeing. We acknowledge that everyone is unique and is an expert in their own experience.

A Note About Language

COMPAS recognises that compassionate language when discussing suicide is important.

Inclusive Language

- “Died by suicide”
- “Took their life”
- “Suicided”
- “Suicide attempt”

The above language works to debunk negative stereotypes and stigma surrounding suicide.

Unhelpful Language

- “Successful suicide”
- “Unsuccessful suicide”
- “Committed suicide”
- “Failed suicide”

The above language present suicide as a desirable outcome and links suicide with crime.

Myths and Misconceptions of Suicide

MYTHS

"Asking a person about suicide will put the idea in their head and encourage them."

"People who attempt suicide are selfish or attention seeking."

"If someone is intent on making a suicide attempt, you cannot stop them."

"If a person is suicidal, they will always feel that way."

"Mental health and suicide risk is low among university students."

FACTS

Asking about suicide does not increase risk. Asking if someone is considering suicide in an open and caring way, can provide an opportunity for them to share how they are feeling and gain support.

There are a range of reasons people suicide including feeling hopeless or emptiness, feeling like a burden, a sense of desperation, or a desire for escape. All suicidal ideation, attempts, or warning signs should be taken seriously.

Suicide is preventable. Interventions, support, and resources can help individuals experiencing suicidal thoughts .

Suicidal thoughts are not permanent, but often increase during times of stress. Appropriate support and services can lessen these thoughts.

Suicide is a leading cause of death for young Australians aged 15-24. In 2021, 322 Australian young people (aged 18–24) took their own lives.

**The above facts and statistics call for an initiative focussed on increased support and early intervention available for those experiencing suicidal thoughts.
This is what COMPAS aims to provide.**

Program Objectives

Overarching Aims

- Support student mental health
- Reduce incidence of suicide
- Assist in connecting students to appropriate resources
- Data based evaluation of program effectiveness

Implementation Guide Aims

- Provide stakeholders with information about the program
- Support institutions in program planning and implementation

COMPAS Principles

- Everyone has potential for change, growth, and resilience
- The uniqueness of each individual deserves respectful and non-judgemental interaction
- COMPAS recognises that people are the experts of their own life, and aims to utilise this expertise to improve wellbeing outcomes
- While COMPAS does not aim to provide therapy, it intends to provide an avenue for building connectedness and empowering service users in their lives
- Assisting students in accessing resources and community to problem solve, and improve their situation and outlook

COMPAS and Improving Early Identification

In an attempt to address some of the issues surrounding effective early suicide identification and intervention, COMPAS builds on the best available contemporary research. With the use of complex algorithms, COMPAS is able to predict with improved accuracy who is at increased risk of suicide.

The model uses a proactive and planned response model to:

- Reach out to the individual
- Complete a more thorough psychosocial assessment with them
- Create a safety plan
- Provide information and recommendations to resources or relevant services as identified
- Follow up at regular intervals

Background

During their studies, more than 90% of university students experience stress. This might be due, but not limited to, finances, health, academic study, and relationships. In any one year, approximately 17% of university students will report experiencing suicidal ideation, 9% make a suicide plan, and 1% attempt to take their own life (Mortier et al., 2018).

Curtin University is part of the World Mental Health International College Student Initiative which explores mental health and early interventions for university students. At more than 18 universities around the world, all incoming first-year students are invited to complete an online survey assessing a range of mental health, physical health, and support factors.

You can find out more about the initiative at:

https://www.hcp.med.harvard.edu/wmh/college_student_survey.php

The complex and constantly changing nature of suicide risk has made it extremely difficult to measure. We have not historically had an assessment tool that measures the probability of suicide risk with enough accuracy to be able to make any real impact on suicide levels to date, worldwide, with the current early suicide identification methods being only approximately 5% effective. Despite increased funding, assessment only brings us slightly above chance levels of accuracy.

Using data from previous cohorts of Curtin students, our research team have developed a program called Checking on Mental Health Providing Alternatives to Suicide (COMPAS). The team have developed a multivariable statistical tool to pre-emptively identify students at future risk of suicidal behaviour in the next 12-months. This new algorithm can identify 53.06% of students who report a subsequent plan or attempt. COMPAS embeds this statistical tool into a wellbeing survey that all incoming first year students are invited to take part in.

Initial evaluation of COMPAS shows that identifying and providing personalised referrals for students identified as at-risk is associated with a 41.7% reduction in the probability of suicidal behaviour one year after the initial phone call. In recognition of the impact this has on university students, our team was awarded the 2022 Curtinovation Award in the teaching and learning category.

The COMPAS program has been developed in consultation with key stakeholders in the university and the community, senior clinical psychologists, people bereaved by suicide, and students with lived experience of suicidal thoughts and behaviours. We are optimistic that COMPAS has a positive impact on the student experience and provides important support to students as they embark on their academic careers. Master of Clinical Psychology Students are a vital part of the COMPAS team, ensuring we listen to the needs of students and offer appropriate resources that match these needs.

Survey Management

- The Qualtrics survey is managed by the research team at Curtin University. The survey asks students for some contact information (name, email, phone) and questions about mental health and stressors.
- An information letter before the survey outlines the procedures and scope of the project for students. Students are provided with contact details to contact the research team or the university's respective Human Research Ethics Office if they have any further questions.
- Students may also access and be directed to the project's FAQs webpage which provides information on the survey and data use.
- The survey is preprogrammed with an algorithm that identifies the students at highest risk for a future suicide plan or attempt.
- Qualtrics is integrated with a secure CRM to assign tasks to clinical trainees and to assign calls to the student using COMPAS. They only get the name and contact details of students, not their survey responses.
- The project team member calls the students identified at high risk. Records of calls are stored in the CRM. Calls are made within 1-2 business days of completion of the baseline survey, and a 4-week follow-up call is also made.
- If a student does not answer the initial phone call after 3 attempts, a research team member will alert the student wellbeing and security team using the CRM for further follow-up.
- Baseline survey data is downloaded and saved in a secure research drive, accessible only to the research team. Identifying information (name, email, phone) is removed from the dataset and replaced with a random ID variable. In a separate dataset, a record is kept of what student IDs correspond to what ID variables (to allow data to be matched to follow-up data).
- 4-weeks after completion of the baseline survey, a 4-week follow-up survey is sent to all students who completed the baseline. 1-year follow-ups are also sent each year the student remains at the university.

The COMPAS Model: Flowchart

Data Management

Identity Verification

- As part of the survey, students are asked to provide their name, email, and student ID, which can be cross-checked against the records provided by the university.
- Students identified as high risk by the algorithm receive a phone call (to the phone number that they provide in their survey answers) from a member of our team, the script for these phone calls opens by asking: “Hi X, I’m [insert caller’s first name] calling from Y university. Can I just confirm that I’m speaking with [confirm student’s name]?” – confirmation is required before continuing the content of the call.

De-identification of Personal Information

Students’ answers on the online surveys are de-identified. These survey responses are downloaded and a random ID number is assigned to each student. In a separate SPSS file, we store a list of student ID numbers with their corresponding random ID number.

In the dataset that contains student answers to the online survey, all identifying student information (student name, email, phone number, student ID number) is removed, and replaced just with the random ID number. These files are stored on the secure research drive in electronic form only.

Records of the phone calls with students identified as high risk are retained in identifiable form, but are kept securely on the CRM. All other data must be either deidentified and stored on the CRM, or deleted after one year.

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Disclosure of Personal Information

Personal information may only be disclosed to the following parties:

- Members of the project team responsible for contacting high-risk students, as they need access to the personal information to contact the correct students.
- Campus security and wellbeing, if our team is unable to contact an at risk student. Campus security and wellbeing will only be provided with the student's contact details (name, student number).
- Emergency services, with student consent and only if during phone call with a student this is judged as necessary to ensure their safety.
- As part of the information provided to students prior to participation in the program, students should be made aware that their next of kin may be contacted if they are presenting as being at risk to themselves or others.

Information Use

- Participants consent to use of their data prior to being able to access the survey. Participants are informed of all data usage in the information letter shown prior to the survey.
- Results of the study will be published in academic journals, presented at international conferences and in de-identified reports prepared for each university. Data may be used to support student research projects (e.g., theses), but individual participants will not be identifiable in any report or student thesis. Data may be used in future research or by COMPAS for program planning purposes. De-identified data is also used to be compared to similar data collected at other universities around the world
- Deidentified data sent overseas to merge with international data for analysis, is stored according to Harvard University's research data security policies (See: <http://vpr.harvard.edu/pages/harvard-research-data-security-policy>). Specifically, in accordance with Australian and WA privacy legislation no identifiable data will be sent to overseas investigators. Data is password protected for sharing though a secure server owned by Harvard University (i.e., data files are not to be emailed).

Training Requirements

General Training Requirements

- All team members must complete Good Clinical Practice (GCP) training to conduct research. GCP Training may be completed online for free (via affiliation with COMPAS) at: <https://retprogram.org/training/ich-good-clinical-practice-gcp-certificate/>
- Any training record forms are to be stored on the Customer Relationship Manager (CRM).

General Responsibilities

- Ethics and governance submissions and monitoring are handled by the core research team, and students where relevant to their academic projects.
- Data confidentiality and privacy is the responsibility of all members. Where a privacy breach has occurred, the Research Lead should be informed, who will notify the Privacy Compliance Officer (Integrity and Standards Unit), who will then make an assessment as to whether the breach should be reported to the relevant regulatory and oversight agencies.
- All team members should also refer to the Data Management Plan (available in the CRM) and ensure that tasks are performed in accordance with these approved plans.

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Telephone Assessment Team

Training Requirements

- The Team lead and Co-investigators for the project will train and supervise all other staff including volunteers who assist with providing assessment and follow-up survey calls, as well as emergency procedures for students at immediate risk (e.g. contacting hospital emergency department).
- Training and supervision in use of the CRM will be conducted by the Team lead and Co-investigators for the project. Further training and guidance can also be provided by the Student Wellbeing Advisory Service Team lead or Service Delivery staff who manage the CRM system

Responsibilities

- Conducting assessment calls with students identified as being at high present or future suicide risk, and providing them with support resources and referral to health providers or advice to attend the emergency department hospital where appropriate.
- Responding to survey queries received via phone or email
- Conducting 1-month follow-up call
- Logging interactions in the CRM system
- Communication with security and wellbeing when a high-risk student has not responded to the team's attempts at contact and requires further follow-up.

Survey Management Team

Training Requirements

- The data manager will train and supervise all other staff including volunteers who assist with activities relating to the survey including training in this policy and procedure
- This may include training in the use of Qualtrics and software used for data analysis and algorithm development.

Responsibilities

- Liaising with the Student Engagement Team for participant/student recruitment
- Maintenance and updates to the survey
- Survey data management and security
- Algorithm development and implementation
- Data analysis
- Liaising with partners/collaborators and stakeholders of the WHO WMH-ICS Initiative (e.g., international partners, funding organisations).

COMPAS Staff Recruitment

In order for clinical trainees to participate in COMPAS it is recommended that all are:

- Enrolled in a Masters of Psychology program which provides them with sufficient clinical and/or counselling skills (e.g. Clinical Psychology).
- Enrolled in a practical placement unit
- Have completed training in Research Integrity

Training and Support

Program Training

All clinical trainees who are involved in the program will engage with online learning modules, and undergo a one-day face-to-face training program, wherein COMPAS models, procedures, and concepts are explained more in-depth. Students are provided with an opportunity to engage in role plays with various levels of risk.

Training Materials

Training in the COMPAS model is provided by Curtin University staff and a comprehensive training manual is provided to assist the Project Manager, Clinical Supervisor, and trainee clinicians in implementation.

Wellbeing and Support

It is recommended that self-care initiatives are available and promoted, including awareness of warning signs of burnout, compassion fatigue, and vicarious trauma. Clinical supervision, social support, physical health promotion, and balance between work, study, and personal life can be important contributors to wellbeing for those involved in implementation of the program.

Key Personnel

Research Lead

Organisation and implementation of data collection, analysis and reporting of the effectiveness of the program.

Project Manager Lead

Operational aspects of Masters of Psychology student recruitment, task allocation, troubleshooting, and quality control.

Clinical Lead

Clinical quality control, clinical reporting, and record keeping.

Clinical Supervisor

Clinical support, debriefing, provision of group supervision of trainee clinicians. Primary escalation point in high risk/crisis situation.

Implementation

Survey Recruitment

- The team at Curtin University has prepared an email text template
- Using the text template, University Administrators will be asked to send an email out to all first year students inviting them to participate in the survey
- After a one-week period, the initial email is followed up with a reminder email alerting students that the survey is still available to them
- Other forms of on-campus advertising will assist in survey recruitment too. This might include, but is not limited to, displaying a slide about the survey in lectures and tutorials, posts on the university's social media platforms, and handing out flyers/pamphlets

Specific Safety Considerations

It is recommended that clinical trainees only make follow up calls while on campus in a suitable environment (eg. Campus Counselling Clinic or Medical Centre) and that two clinical trainees work together to action the calls so that one student is available to contact emergency services if required, while the other engages with the follow up call.

Onsite services may need to be involved thus making key personnel aware of the COMPAS program is advised.

Public Mental Health Services

Where possible it is recommended that collaborations are established with existing publicly available services so that higher risk students can be followed up by clinical staff.

Linking in with existing services who are cognisant of COMPAS may mean that processes can be streamlined to ensure timely and appropriate support for students. Different services may have different policies regarding follow up when a student does not engage, so ensuring that external services have compatible processes and capacity to be proactive in student support is important for the fidelity of the model.

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